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CURRENT PERSPECTIVE ON NOVEL DELIVERY SYSTEM FOR MANAGEMENT ON NON-SMALL CELL LUNGS CANCER: COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) is a type of lung cancer and presently a prominent cause for death among the cancer cases globally. It includes adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma and large cell carcinoma. Because of the limitations of the conventional strategies in safety and efficacy, advancement in the respective field has occurred gradually from past to present. Surgery act as a care of standard in operable early stage NSCLC. At present, trimodality approach (surgery, radiation, chemotherapy) has gained popularity in the treatment of advance stage NSCLC. Chemotherapy is associated with chemo-resistance and it is a hindrance to achieve the success. Innovative irradiation technique and pre-chemotherapy irradiation is being effective than standard radiation therapy. Targeted therapy is now increasingly used because of its long term disease control by blocking the important pathway. Various management strategies are being used for management of NSCLC which are highlighted in this study. Radiofrequency ablation (RFA), immunotherapy, personalized therapy, gene therapy has a good impact in the effective treatment of NSCLC by increasing survival rate. The present review enwraps information about available approaches and strategies which are intended for the treatment of NSCLC.

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INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer is the most frequently diagnosed malignant disorder and contribute for the significant role in the death of cancer patient globally.^{1,2} As per the fact, lung cancer is regarded as the most life taking disease among all of the cancer all over the world. Data of the surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Result (SEER) from 2004-2008 suggested that lung and bronchus cancer are diagnosed at median age of 71 years. They also found that reporting of lung cancer as per the as groups: <20 years; (no cases reported), 20-34 years; (0.2%), 35-44 years; (1.5%), 45-54 years; (8.8%), 55-64 years; (20.9%), 65-74 years; (31.1%), 75-84 years (29%), 85 years and older (8.3%).¹ It has been known that death due to lung cancer are associated with cigarette smoking and understanding this fact of epidemiology and other factors has laid an additional base in the lung cancer prevention.³

OBJECTIVE

Main objective of our review was to focus on:

- Treatment trend for Non -Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC)
- Risk factor associated with lung cancer.
- Explaining available option for treatment and advancement.
- Diagnosis trend for Non -Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC)

Lung cancer is broadly classified in two categories: Non -Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC) and Small Cell Lung Cancer (SCLC). Among these two types 85% is classified as NSCLC. The five year survival rate is less than 10% in the patient with NSCLC. It is further divided in three subtypes: squamous cell carcinoma, adenocarcinoma, and large cell carcinoma. They accounts for ~20%, 38.5%, 2.9% of all cancer cases respectively.³ SCLC is a type of lung cancer which is highly malignant tumor originating from the cell with neuroendocrine characteristics. It contributes for remaining 15% of lung cancer.³

Adenocarcinoma is originated from alveolar, bronchiolar epithelial cells. SCLC is linked with smoking habit and history and it is centrally located and originated from bronchia epithelium.²

Symptoms of NSCLC includes Cough, dyspnea, hoarseness, weight loss, chest pain, wheezing, hemoptysis, anorexia, nausea/vomiting, swelling of face and arm, fatigue, bone pain, clubbing, headache, seizure etc.⁵

As per the survey done in 2008 new diagnosis of lung cancer were made (>1.6 million, 13% of new cancer diagnosed) and they found that lung cancer death accounted for 18% (1.4 million) among all the cancer deaths.⁴

RISK FACTORS:

MAJOR RISK FACTORS:

Cigarette smoking, air pollution, occupational hazards like working in mine and exposure to cooking oil, Uranium, Crystalline silica and chrysotile asbestos, genetic susceptibility TP53 germline sequence and individual with these sequence crave more for nicotine so it increases the chance of lung cancer in smokers.⁶ The occurrence of the lung cancer is greatly associated with the habit of smoking in an individual. There is an existence of relation between passive and active smoking which can be understood by 1.6% of lung cancers.⁶ A study revealed that SCLC and squamous cell carcinomas had shown to be associated with both active and passive smoking.⁷ Continuous exposure to the ambient air pollution with polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon compound brings up the risk of development of lung cancer. Lung cancer in Europe is estimated to be 11% due to the urban air pollution.⁶

OTHERS RISK FACTORS:

Some evidences supports the association of lung cancer with low serum level of Beta-carotene.⁸ In patient with NSCLC, with C type of CYP2E1 suggest that the patient at a greater risk to develop squamous cell carcinoma due to impaired ability of body to metabolize certain carcinogens which leads to P53 gene mutation.⁹

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY:

The lung cancer starts by the exposure of carcinogens either exogenous or endogenous for long period of time leads to continuous tissue damage which induces stimulation for cell proliferation to repair those damaged tissues. The deactivated anti-tumor immunity provides the favorable environment for malignant transformed cells to live.¹⁰ Lung cancer being a reason for most of the cancer death, the distinction between NSCLC and SCLC is of immense importance regarding tumor genetics and biology.¹¹ Genetic susceptibility and family history of COPD and lung cancer has a significant contribution in progression of lung cancer. Association of 3p14-23 chromosomal deletion was depicted by Whang-Peng in a study which was commonly observed in NSCLC. Autocrine growth factor (bombosin -peptide), epigenetic gene activation leads to gene mutation, transformation, proliferation of tumor cells of lungs.¹¹ In NSCLC, EGFR receptor deregulation of tyrosine kinase (TKs) and mutation of this gene are likely to be a factor in the pathogenesis of lung cancer. ALK in NSCLC is normally forming a ALK- fusion protein with other gene and mutation of other genes also have the role in pathogenesis of NSCLC.¹² Alteration or defect in certain proto-oncogene, genetic changes of tumor suppressor gene has a contributory support in the multi stage development of lung cancer.¹³ Hypomethylation in certain CpG site of AHRR and F2RL3 gene has strong bonding with smoking and has greater risk associated for lung cancer.¹⁴ A study concluded that TAZ shows the lentivirus mediated overexpression of TAZ in epithelial cell of bronchi and showed result in cell overgrowth and its transformation and act as potent oncogene for potentiation of NSCLC carcinogenicity.¹⁵ Mendelian co-dominant inheritance is associated with the evolution of lung cancer in early age with the involvement of rare major autosomal gene.¹⁶

A study found out the loss of heterozygosity at 8p21-23 with the deletion at chromosome 3P and 9P due to which they concluded that allelic loss at 8p21-23 are associated early event in the pathogenesis of lung cancer.¹⁷ Some studies have also demonstrated that leptin enhances the DNA synthesis process and growth of the cell through various signaling cascade like JAK/STAT, ERK1/2, PKC-a pathways.¹⁸

TYPES AND STAGING OF LUNG CANCER:

Pathophysiological classification of lung cancer is majorly classified as non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) small cell lung cancer (SCLC). NSCLC has 3 major classifications as adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, large cell carcinoma. Staging of cancer is defined as the measure to describe intensity of the cancer spreading and provides the platform to plan the best treatment option. An effective staging system is TNM system of staging which stages the cancer by considering size of tumor (T), whether the lymph node have cancer cells or not (N), and metastasis (M) spread of tumor away from lungs and lymph node or not.

- T₁ if the tumor is less than 3 centimeters (<3cm) in size. T₂ if tumors more than 3 cm not exceeding 7cm (3 to <7cm). T₃ if tumor is more than 7 cm and has extended to breathing tubes or lining of the lungs or spine beyond the lungs. T₄ if the tumor has spread to the heart, major blood vessels, esophagus or spine.
- N₀ if no cancer found in lymph nodes. N₁ if tumor was found ipsilateral peri-bronchial and/or ipsilateral hilar and intrapulmonary lymph nodes. N₂ if tumor has spread to ipsilateral mediastinal and/or subcarinal lymph nodes. N₃ if the tumor is found in contralateral mediastinal, contralateral hilar, ipsilateral or contralateral scalene or supraclavicular lymph nodes.
- M₀ if no known metastasis. M_{1a} if contralateral pleural nodules or pleural dissemination was found. M_{1b} if tumor has spread to distant organs.¹⁹

DIAGNOSIS:

Diagnosis of lung can be made considering various parameters and some advance and distinctive parameters can be summarized as:

- Diagnosis of NSCLC can be done by determination of serum marker level of EGF, SCD26, calprotectin, matrix metalloproteinase-1,-7,-9, CEA and CYFRA21 for NSCLC (94% sensitive) and SCLC (100% sensitive).²⁰
- Plasma miR-92a-2 level is higher in SCLC patient so this test can be of potential in diagnosing SCLC.²¹
- Some rare cases like diaphragmatic metastases can be diagnosed by chest X-ray and abdominal-pelvic computed tomography which is further followed by immune histochemical exam revealing cytokeratin-7 positive and negative for cytokeratin20, which suggest primary lung tumor as adenocarcinoma.²²
- SF, CEA, CA242, NSE, CA125, CA19-9 and CA15-3 are tumor serum biomarker, combining observation of two clinical indicators and two of the above biomarkers with the help of model.²³

SURGERY

Surgery for cancer has gained its wide acceptance in last decade with enormous implications in adenocarcinoma in early stage lesion.² By the use of surgical approaches preoperative morbidity and mortality has been greatly reduced.²⁴ In NSCLC with stage I and II, resection acts as a primary method of treatment and acts as the best caring measure in early stage without advancement of the disease. Less invasive approaches like VATS (Video Assisted Thoracoscopic Surgery) should be considered and with advanced stage like stage 3A, multimodality regimen should be considered.²⁵ Surgery is an important step in selective patients of stage 3 and 4 and palliation with the advanced stage of disease.²⁶ Nicolaos et al. conducted a study on surgical approaches for lung cancer and found out that the N₂ signifies spectrum and inter phase of surgery and non-surgical process of treatment. They concluded "lobectomy, a gold standard". In N₀ lobectomy is possible.²⁷ Gonzolavarela conducted a study and concluded that among the total cases of NSCLC 75% are diagnosed with advanced stage (3a and 4) and this option is found to be the best in IIIA(N₂) stage after starting chemotherapy and lobectomy with systemic model dissection recommendation in unexpected N₂ case. In case of resectable T₄N₀=1 in stage 3B surgery remains its self only choice.²⁸ YOKOUCHI H. found that T₃N₀M₀ case was surgically treated and the extra pleural dissection, complete resection measures were successful to announce 5 years rate of NSCLC patients.²⁹ In a study by NHENYANG DAI et al, also found that lobectomy was better option than segmentectomy or wedge resection in overall survival of lung cancer. NSCLC less than equal to 1 cm and more than 1 to 2 cm, lobectomy is unfavorable. Therefore, segmentectomy can be performed.³⁰ A study Hong Shen et al, described that the survival of the patient was found to be more on who had undergone surgery than who didn't in stage IV.³¹ In the current trend due to its decrease invasiveness and increase effectiveness, resection in T_{1a} tumors is gaining its popularity.³²

RADIATION THERAPY:

Radiation therapy, name itself suggest that the use of radiation to kill the tumor cell and alleviate the symptoms of cancer in individual who have undergone stereotactic body radiation therapy (SBRT). In the condition of inoperable NSCLC the survival rate was 55.8% at 3 years and the study shows that use of SBRT can achieve high rate of tumor control. Mainly it is effective in early stage of NSCLC.³³ By the introduction of SBRT, the use of radiation therapy was found to be increased by 16% in elderly patient with the result of increase of improvement in overall survival.³⁴ Innovative irradiation delivery technique and some irradiation before chemotherapy had increased the survival rate compared to those receiving standard radiation therapy. Surgically unresectable stages like III A, II, IIIB NSCLC are most favorable condition for radiation therapy. There is a proven fact that chemotherapy followed by radiation therapy was found to be superior to any other regimen.³⁶ In NSCLC patient with medically inoperable stage first condition curative radiation therapy (CR) can be given.³⁵ A sequential approach is better option rather than the combined one but it is associated with the incident of toxicities in higher dose. Combining Hyper Fractionized Radiation Therapy and concurrent carbon platinum and etoposide (CVDCA/BP16), the result was found to be effective than HFXRT alone.³⁷

In a study by Ronald C .MC.grayete al, the maximum tolerated dose in T2 stratum was found to be 72 Gy for tumor larger than 5 cm and concluded that SBRT is a safe and effective for the treatment of early stage lung cancer in the patient with medically inoperable condition. Local control was achieved in its excellence.³⁸ HCHOY et al. found that, in patient with locally advanced NSCLC the therapy constituting PACLITAXEL, carboplatin and radiation therapy produces a treatment modality with high response rate and acceptable toxicity with increase survival rate.³⁹ Mostly the RT is considered in stage 3 NSCLC patient by using Positron Emission Tomography (PET) with 18-F flurodeoxy glucose (FDG) is effective in detecting unsuspected metastasis so PET staging should be of recommendation for radical candidates of NSCLC and frequently with stage III.⁴⁰

A different treatment approach using radiation for the treatment with the potential therapeutic efficacy to treat NLCLC is Boron Neutron Capture Therapy (BNCT) which combines biological targeting and high Linear Energy Transfer (LET). MEC source was effective for shallow NSCLC (depth of 6cm) and course is short. MIT source was found to be effective in deep long tumor (depth of 9 cm).⁴¹

In a study by child patient with unresectable NSCLC were followed till the death and the result was favorable with stage III with the treatment in combined modality of CHT and RT.⁴² Study by James k Rusoet al. on IMRT (Intensity-Modulated Radiation Therapy)and CT in advanced inoperable NSCLC found that IMRT was well tolerated by NSCLC patient pneumonitis and esophagitis like toxicities were observed.⁴³ CHART (Continuous Hyper fractionated Accelerated Radiotherapy) showed better in survival of patient with NSCLC.⁴⁴ A study by Christina Schroder showed that the 74 GY total radiation treatment has the better future as suitable treatment in condition of NSCLC.⁴⁵

CHEMOTHERAPY:

Post-operative chemotherapy in resectable stage-I and II NSCLC is now being considered as standard care.² At present trimodality therapy (chemotherapy, radiation, surgery) has gained popularity for the treatment of resectable, locally advanced NSCLC.⁴⁶ Recent study by Soria JC, et al. found that Ceritinib used as first line therapy showed a statistically significant and clinically acceptable enhancement in the progression free survival in patient with ALK-rearranged NSCLC than by platinum based regimen.⁴⁷

For first line treatment of NSCLC Gemcitabin as monotherapy and single agent taxanes and vinorelbine were considered. But the combination of docetaxel and cisplatin was found to be superior combination than vinorelbineand cisplatin to increase the survival rate in the patients with NSCLC.⁴⁸ Study by Frank V Fossella et al. found that docetaxel in second line therapy had shown increased survival rate along with the increased time for disease progression.⁴⁹ Patient with unsuitability for cisplatin based regimen, monotherapy is preferable choice. For second line therapy anti folate pemetrexed had shown better efficacy than docetaxel with significant reduction in toxicity. Erlotinib can also be used as second or third line therapy.⁵⁰ A study by F.A Shepherd claimed that the use of erlotinib in advanced NSCLC prolongs the survival after first or second line chemotherapy.⁵¹ Mitomycin C and vinorelbine were also accepted as second line therapy inspite of docetaxel and pemetrexed were of choice.⁵² Although trimodality therapy has gained popularity in NSCLC the radiation in chemotherapy do not have any superiority over neoadjuvant chemotherapy.⁵³ Adjunctive therapy has survival benefit in IB and IIIA NSCLC patient but neoadjuvant is found to be better tolerated than post-surgical adjuvant therapy.⁵⁴ The platinum based regimen is considered asa gold standard chemotherapy but it is associated with chemo-resistance which is acting as a hindrance in achieving the success of the therapy in NSCLC.^{55,56}

A study by Weiss J. et al. made clear that the Nano-particle Albumin Bound(nab) paclitaxel/carboplatin has significantly greater response rate than in paclitaxel/ carboplatin given every 3weeks (q3w) in stage-IV NSCLC patients.⁵⁷

TARGETED THERAPY:

Targeted therapy is an approach which affects the cellular mechanism which gives promotion for cancer cell viability and proliferation with the involvement of the pathways like hormonal axis, growth factor receptor mediated tyrosine kinase, cellular immune system. TKIs stops transduction and checkpoint inhibitors recognize and destructs the cancer cells by cytotoxic T-cell.⁵⁸ Substantial development in the field of targeted therapy has given a promising strategy to treat advanced metastatic NSCLC. Addition of bevacizumab or cetuximab and erlotinib and gefitinib for second line therapy has given a positive outcome and the explorative knowledge about cancer biology and tumorigenesis at present has aided to develop molecular target and novel target therapies.⁵⁹ The hallmark of the targeted therapy is to block some important pathways which aids in suppression of cancer progression and achieving the long ter disease control.⁶⁰

In lung adenocarcinoma and Squamous Cell Carcinoma the oncogenic driver for mutation is known, which stimulates complex cascade of cross signaling pathways like JAK-STAT, PI3K-AKT-mTOR etc. Due to this stimulation uncontrolled growth, proliferation and survival of cancer cell and here comes the role of targeted therapy to identify and inhibit the up regulation of these pathways by different mechanism. Studies now are focusing in the mutation inhibitions by receptor monoclonal antibodies (mab) or tyrosine kinase inhibitor (TKI). And in the decades earlier they had demonstrated the successful inhibition of the mutation of EGFR and fusion of ALK by EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitors and crizotinibrespectively.⁶¹The available agents for the targeted therapy in NSCLC are crizotinib, erlotinib, gefitinib, bevacizumab. Erlotinib or gefitinib is considered as indicated first line treatment option in the patient of NSCLC with activating EGFR mutation and crizotinib is indicated first line treatment for ALK-positive patient. Bevacizumab can be used as first line in combination with chemotherapy and can be continued till the severe or unacceptable toxicities appears.⁶²

Gefitinib targeted therapy is associated with drug resistance in NSCLC.⁶³ Pembrolizumab has effect in PD-L1 expression with untreated NSCLC which is untreated with platinum based chemotherapy. It has shown clinical benefit by increasing progression free survival, overall survival, and objective response. It is now acting as a promising strategy in treatment of NSCLC.⁶⁴ Use of MET-tyrosine kinase inhibitors (MET-TKIs) has the potential benefits against resistance of targeted therapy in NSCLC which has been demonstrated by recent research and reviews.⁶⁵ NSCLC responds frequently to TKIs such as erlotinib in condition of activating mutation EGFR. AXL expression in lung cancer with EGFR mutation has laid a promising therapeutic target to inhibit resistance.⁶⁶ The newer agent cetuximab; an anti-EGFR monoclonal antibody is showing activity in both first and second line treatment of NSCLC.⁶⁷

A study by Raefelrosell, et al. says that ERCC1 mRNA overexpression in NSCLC showed lower response to cisplatin based therapy whereas ribonucleotide reductase mRNA overexpression showed lower response to gemcitabine.⁶⁸ ALK is considered as key oncogenic driver in advanced NSCLC.⁶⁹ crizotinib ; a FDA approved small molecule which is ALK/MET/ROS1 inhibitor has shown its dominating effectiveness in treatment of locally advanced and metastatic NSCLC expressing ALK.^{70,71} In some studies they had mentioned that the combination of EGFR inhibitors in the chemotherapy had shown no benefit.⁷²

Fig1: Treatment algorithm of crizotinib in NSCLC.

A study performed by Guillermo Lopezvivano, et al. suggested that bevacizumab with cisplatin and pemetrexed are approved as a first line therapy in squamous cell NSCLC.⁷³ Trastuzumab is a monoclonal antibody directed against HER2 has a synergistic effect with cytotoxic drugs. The potential of this agent was observed that it targets to the altered protein and the positive result was observed in treatment of NSCLC.⁷⁴

IMMUNOTHERAPY:

Immune therapy is broadly classified as active and passive. Active immunity refers to the distinction between normal cell and cancer cell by host immunity. And passive immunity can be understood as an active agent that functions outside the body which is not related to host machinery function immunologically. The most popular passive immunotherapy is monoclonal antibodies which blocks and destroys tumorigenic cascade.⁷⁵ Lung cancer being immune resistant disease immunotherapy for solid tumors and drugs to immune response has made revolutionary enhancement in the field of therapy of NSCLC.⁷⁶ Study of the interaction within tumors and immune system has resulted in the development of immunotherapy for NSCLC. Adoptive cell transfer such as cytokine-induced killer, $\gamma\delta$ T-cells are the newly introduced advancement in the field of immunotherapy for NSCLC.⁷⁷

Immunotherapy and chemotherapy schedule or immunotherapy alone are being used and are under investigations for promising benefit in treating NSCLC in near future.⁷⁸ Immunotherapy strategy has proved to be beneficial for early and advanced stage NSCLC with good tolerance and with durability in its response.⁷⁹ This option could be superior when molecular target therapy, vaccine, and chemotherapy are combined. In the present context mAbs and vaccine are most effective and promising agents of this family.⁸⁰ With the various present advancement in this modality life expectancy has increased in condition of metastatic NSCLC.⁸¹ Restoration of antitumor immune response is a key strategy for the stoppage of cancer cell survival and progression. So the agent like cytotoxic-t-lymphocyte associated antigen-4 receptor and PD-1 receptor which act as immune checkpoint targeting agent have shown satisfactory tumor response and survival in NSCLC.⁸²

Pembrolizumab and Nivolumab which are monoclonal antibodies for blocking PD-1 receptor T-cell binding with death ligand (PD-L1) within the tumor cell of the individual. So the immune system responds against cancer cells vigorously.⁸³ Antigen-Independent immune modulated strategy and vaccine therapy has some evidences of better outcome by enhancing antitumor immune response and synergetic effect with chemotherapy in treating NSCLC.⁸⁴

A study by valsamo.k.anagnostou et al. focused in scientific revolution in NSCLC immunotherapy. Amplifying the host immune response opposite of tumor helps to reduce the tumor progression. By the suppression of inhibition pathways like CTL antigen-4 (CTLA-4) and PD-1 with mAbs had created the antitumor efficacy.⁸⁵ If the comparison is made between cisplatin based therapy and immunotherapy with low dose IL-2 and pineal hormone melatonin (MLT), the survival time was found more with the immunotherapy than chemotherapy.⁸⁶

A study by Christian manegold MD, et al. reviewed about the possibilities of combined immunotherapy and anti-angiogenesis for synergetic treatment in advanced NSCLC and found that modulation of immune response by decreasing the infiltration of T-cell in microenvironment of tumor and by immune regulatory cell functions.⁸⁷ Tumor-induced immune suppression is being observed in the malignant disease progression. Immune therapy is the strategy to increase the patient innate immune response and leading to induction of long term response in patient with NSCLC and SCLC. Lung cancer patient treated with anti-PD-1, the result was found to be superior in overall survival (OS) than chemotherapy in second line therapy.⁸⁸

RADIOFREQUENCY ABLATION (RFA):

Radiofrequency ablation (RFA) is a new and advanced approach to treat the tumors. It is used in primary and metastatic lung cancer at present days increasingly with the sole curative intension and further more is yet to be explored. It destroys the viability of selected tumors by the image guidance technique. And in case of lung cancer it is being as an attractive option with minimal invasion and has attained sustained reserve in lung cancer.^{89,90} By the studies in the past also demonstrated it as a safe and the therapy with the promising procedure with technical feasibility to treat inoperable NSCLC and metastases and are considered as a no-invasive in high risk patients of NSCLC.⁹¹ RFA has peculiar advantage compared to conventional radiotherapies and surgical treatment as it has ability to show increased survival time with the minimum risk associated for complications.⁹²

RFA is considered in inoperable condition. In patient with pulmonary malignancies the response to RFA was high and was sustained complete response in high proportion. And use of RFA was observed safe and effective as well as practical method in palliative treatment for painful NSCLC with chest wall metastasis.^{93,94} It has complete ablation and the result observed was excellent in the tumor sized less than 2-3 cm. It is effective primarily in stage-I NSCLC for long period of time with minimal invasion.^{95,96} For stage -I inoperable patient who are under RFA following conventional radiotherapy, the survival rate and local control was found better with RFA than radiotherapy alone.⁹⁷

A study undertaken by Omae k. et al. on long term survival after RFA of lungs oligometastasis they concluded that the overall survival and progress free survival improvement are promise by RFA of lung oligometastasis from 5 primary lesion.⁹⁸ Michael.D. chan, et al. studied about combination of RFA with high dose rate (HDR) brachytherapy for early stage NSCLC and found that subsequent therapy of RFA with HDR-brachytherapy has local control in its excellence and toxicity profile in inoperable early stage high risk patient of NSCLC are acceptable.⁹⁹

GENE THERAPY:

Gene therapy is defined as the technology which primarily aims in modification of the genetic component within the cell to achieve the therapeutic goal of an agent.¹⁰⁰ Gene therapy utilizes the process of transferring specific genetic material to produce certain impact in disease pathology. So the knowledge and understanding of the pathogenesis of lung cancer is must. It finds good impact in condition like locally advanced or metastatic disease so it is advantageous in lung cancer to prevent disease related mortality and morbidity.¹⁰¹ As a result of various study in past decades there occurred introduction of various gene therapy procedure like blocking of altered tumor promoting oncogenes, replacing the inactivated tumor suppressor genes and apoptosis promoting gene. And due to this an implication can be drawn as it can be of immense importance in treating lung cancer.¹⁰²

Poly β -amino ester (PBAEs) is found effective for intracellular DNA delivery recently. PEGylated form of PBAE polyplexes helps in maintaining stability and the therapeutic efficacy in intracellular delivery to lung cancer cells of human is not compromised. So by these studies it is made clear that these polymers have specificity and potency for treating lung cancer as a gene therapy.¹⁰³ The biodegradable polyamine like Spermine (SPE) which are synthesized with PEG-diacrylate (SPE-alt-PEG) acts as a vector. And when folic acid (FA) is incorporated (FA-SPE-PEG) gives enhanced transfection performance which established itself as a prospective targeted gene delivery vector and has high transfection power with biocompatibility at its best.¹⁰⁴

A study done by Mariacamelasantarpi, et al. on xerodermapigmentosum group D (XPD). And ribonucleotide reductase subunit M1 (RRM1) polymorphism in the patient with stage-III A-B NSCLC and they found that polymorphism in single nucleotide of XPD312 acts as a prognostic factor for survival for locally advanced NSCLC patients treated with neoadjuvant gemcitabine/cisplatin/docetaxel followed by surgery.¹⁰⁵ By identifying the gene involving for progression of disease, a new molecular target or gene alteration can be done to reach the desired therapeutic outcome.¹⁰⁶ Anti-tumor effect can be achieved by dendritic cell (DC) bioengineered with tumor-associated antigen (TAA) which establish the probability to explore itself for anti-cancer strategy.¹⁰⁷

PERSONALISED THERAPY:

It is a therapy that aims right therapy for right person.¹⁰⁸ Personalized therapy is procedure to separate patient in different group and stratum is treated as per disease nature. By the recent study and resulting discovery about activating mutation in EGFR and fusion gene ALK has described the basic platform for personalized therapy.¹⁰⁹ To use this therapy first knowledge about tumor biology should be adequate as this therapy potential to increase survival in the patient. And the personalized therapy distinctly used in NSCLC are treating patient of NSCLC with activating EGFR mutation and patient of NSCLC with genetic aberration in ALK oncogene by using mesenchymal-epithelial transition factor (MET)/ ALK inhibitor crizotinib. And various new approaches are under investigations.¹¹⁰ There is increasing trend in development of personalized therapy where nucleotide-excision repair (NER) based personalized therapy is a versatile example and has potential for enhancing treatment approach in NSCLC.¹¹¹

Personalized therapy focuses on the delivery of the drug to particular oncogenic pathway which is active in tumor and it deals with the enormous intension to achieve best response rate. New generation sequencing technology has aided to this therapy by multiple molecule alterations.¹¹² TKIs are considered as a first line therapy in advanced NSCLC with EGFR mutation under the personalized therapy.¹¹³ The Biomarker-integrated Approach of Targeted Therapy for Lung Cancer Elimination (BATTLE) Trial showed the satisfactory disease control which set a pattern for personalized approach in NSCLC.¹¹⁴

Based on the EGFR mutant or wildtype the treatment can be personalized as per the effectiveness and selectivity in the person for right therapy which can be demonstrated by the following algorithm.¹¹⁵

Fig 2: Algorithm for personalized therapy in EGFR mutation.

CONCLUSION

Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) is most leading cause of the cancer death in global scenario and it accounts for the 80% of the lungs cancer cases. The present trend is being established in anticancer approaches with the sole intent to efface the presence of cancer cells with consideration of safety and efficacy of the treatment. In this review article I focused on the available approaches for anticancer treatment of NSCLC and the advancement and its impact on treatment. The combination of radiation with chemotherapy is associated with better outcome than any of the strategies alone. Crizotinib is a promising agent for the treatment of NSCLC for present and future.

CONFLICT OF INTREST

I confirm that this article does not contain any conflict of interest.

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